

Volume 2 Number 1 June 2009

MUKABALA

Journal of Performing Arts and Culture

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**Performance as Enterprise:
The Calabar Carnival of Cross River State, Nigeria**

C.L. Okam

Department of Theatre and Performing Arts Ahmadu Bello University,
Zaria

Resume

L'auteur decrit le camaval comme un genre du theatre. Elle considere la pertinence du camaval du point de vue d'entreprise sur le plan d'innovation aussi bien que creativite tout comme une initiative d'entrepreneur. L'auteur

va un peu plus loin pour avancer que le camaval en tant qu'une presentation theatrale sert le triple objectif de divertir, de preserver les cultures et de generer des fonds. Elle soutient en conclusion que le camaval tout en etant une source de revenue peut aussi servir a ouvrir de nouveaux horizons aux presentations theatrales dans les Etats Africains modernes et a donner une nouvelle vie au theatre Africain en general.

Introduction

The notion of carnival involves a public celebration or jubilant road work and an amalgam of masque, masquerade, dances, and costumed revels among other things. It is a showcase of cultural value and heritage of the people in a refined secular form. Bonnie Costello puts it more clearly: "Carnival is that state or domain in which the norms of culture are violated or inverted and in which repressed anxieties and desires find expression...It is Dionysian in an agnostic as well as in ecstatic fashion" (1993:76).

It certainly reflects man's value of his heritage and his expression of an ideational experience. Carnival is predicated upon the concern of a proved tradition of demystifying the ideas of the people in the terrains of entertainment by destroying the barricades of a bottled art through enforcing conformity and the spirit of free representation of all individuals in an acceptable social terrain. Carnival portrays the 'liminal' (Turner 1967 p from the serious to the ordinary enactment creating an atmosphere representation with costume, colors and characters and within a re space or as defined by the camivalesque presentation.

Indisputably carnival falls under the classification of Performance arts. This is because performance art embraces the creation of new syntheses with other arts; dramatic, theatrical, visual and textual-a combination that elucidates totality. This goes with Richard Schechner (in Martin et. al. ed. 2000: ii) who is of the view that: "Performance as a theoretical category and as a practice has expanded explosively. It now comprises panoply of genres ranging from play, to popular entertainments, to theatre, dance, and music, to secular acts and rituals, to performance in everyday life, to intercultural experiments and more". Performance operates within the construct of time and space and the performer/audience relationship. Elin Diamond (1996:1) clearly articulates the meaning of performance in this descriptive term, '...as a doing and a thing done. Certain embodied acts in specific site, witnessed by others (and/or the watching self)... it is the thing done, completed event framed in time and space and remembered, misremembered, interpreted and passionately revisited across a pre-existing discursive field'. The performance arts is built on the structural framework of the functions transmitted from what was done (the art) to who is watching what was done. For example, one can imagine oneself during childhood- passing through a craftsman's house and the view of a finished*product like the drum will stir dancing in one and other children just because one is familiar with the sound it can produce or had seen it used by a good drummer. Just like the imagining of an elderly man of chiefly mien when confronted with the ceremonial hand fan, rattles and a whole of them in advance of its functional explication. If one looks to that area of performance taken together one gets the feel of performative synthesis that evokes total experience for the physical body and the soul. Harding (2000:3-8) states the effective nature of this art with the following explication: 'a preferred form of iteration, explication and reinforcement of social order in a primarily oralate society' like Africa. Those who watch inadvertently confirm their adherence to or dissension from the social order by their presence or absence- at the performance and by their appropriate applause. She asserts that it is a primary forum for the exploration of new ideas, a new order. The performance art is produced in the 'self of the artist' seen and heard through the presence, voice or movement and its temporality existence verified by the presence of the spectators.

Performance necessarily means an expression fostered by phenomenon, delivered through the creativity of an artist for the purpose of consumption. It involves the experiential role of the audience and performer,

but above all it is a movement, not a monument of a particular phenomenon presented, represented through effective action.

Spiritual, serious, entrepreneurial, playful and entertaining are the different forms of performance arts that can be presented/represented and different people may react in different ways as it strikes them, but the unchanging thing is its transformational validity respected and appreciated by the performer/audience and the art. First is the transformation of the ordinary space and time. Highlighting the spatial relations, Okwori (1998) acknowledges that the market in the traditional core serves more than the functions of buying and selling. It is the meeting point of the spirits and humans and it is the arena of performance especially in the African society. This is because in most traditional contexts performance is an occasion for contact and interaction between mortals and spirits, done to maintain a symbiotic relationship between the world of the living, the dead and the unborn Soyinka (1978). The second transformational stint is the transformation of the performer and the audiences as exemplified in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* (1958: 64) "Though Okonkwo's wives and others might have recognized the 'egwugwu' he has transformed into through his springy walk, they still see it as the dead fathers of the clan." At that point in time the belief system prevails over the secular use of the space. Everybody mythically follow the transformation.

From the foregoing, the paper uses the above explication of performance as a theoretical grounding to argue that carnival rejuvenates the idea of a performance art genre. The paper indicates that carnival's potential lies in its structural design and pedigree- a design that has been aptly called total arts. It is a structure that delivers relevance and strikes at the spiritual and social yearning of individuals and communities. The structure projects the essence of carnival validation, and establishes and re-establishes a cultural rootedness or sense of belongings. As Boal 1979 correctly observes

'Theater'.. was the people singing freely in the open air; the theatrical performance was created by and for the people, and thus could be called dithyrambic song. It was a celebration in which all could participate freely.

By this, Boal is alluding to the liberative character of traditional theatre. A theatre that gives free atmosphere to individual and collective creative expression, a theatre that fulfills the yearnings of the soul and feeds the spirit by enabling the individual and collective to sing, dance, move, feel and experience some form of therapy of purged burdens. Boal echoes what all along has been known by man about the power of theatre. The carnival provides an enabling environment where every body participates in the free square, connecting to what they are familiar with unlike the conventional/classical theatre where the actors and the spectators are separated. It accepted all classes of people, showcasing their individual creative enterprise.

Carnivals express themselves through the principles of a world upside down on the plat form of daily reality of the social order and the inverted world of laughter and folly. Carnival is thus a licensed inversion of 'bipolar oppositions' (Bakhtin, 1968) which was expected by authorities to express social solidarity and harmless laughter Lev-Aladgem (2000:164). Lev-Aladgem argues that cotemporary carnivals do not necessarily carry this meaning, but functions as a political means to express a desire for social change. In addition, contemporary carnival's evolutionary process relates to economic development due to the space created for business ventures.

Carnivals exist all over the world, examples of the Jamaican carnival (Nettleford 2003), the Trinidad and Tobago carnival (Hill 1997) and others. Also there are examples of contemporary carnivals like the carnival of Rio de Janeiro, the Ness carnival in France, the Mardi Gras Carnival in New Orleans Lev-Aladgem (2000) the Abuja Carnival and the discourse of concern-Calabar Carnival both of Nigeria.

The twin Island of Trinidad and Tobago is a good example of carnival's transition to contemporary form. This carnival began as a pre-Lenten festival of the elite French and French Creole population. Described as a festival of inversion by Milla C. Riggio (1998:12). The inverted form of the festival is ascribed because of its association with profanations, sexuality, parody and other excesses. It was also a period of show of resistance, emancipation, or rather summed in Riggio's words as '...a key event through which the people perform and in the process reformulate a sense of personal and social identity, (1998:21). The carnival as described

by John Cupid (Riggio 1998:102) provides opportunities to the claiming and reclaiming of self and space and being, and also defense from *perceived and actual threats* (emphasis is mine) However, it has moved from this space of excessive characteristics of political satire and inversion of social order for entertainment purpose as found in the traditional carnival to fit into the commercial/ economic parlance, along side the initial essence either as a conceptualized force or a force of providence possibly to alleviate ‘perceived and actual threats’ of economics recession. In the light of these carnivals the Abuja carnival was formulated.

Abuja carnival of Nigeria started in the year 2005 under the democratic regime of president Olusegun Obasanjo has its origin described as “a reaction to the carnivals of other nations that he had been invited to, he observed that these carnivals had historical experiences and contributed immensely to the cultural growth of their countries in addition to projecting the images of these countries”. It centers on the cultural angle- thereby showcasing the cultural diversity of the different ethnic groups in the country as well as their oneness in the whole gamut of traditionalism, while the Carnival Calabar elucidates the space of defence against ‘perceived and actual threats’ literally and metaphorical by showcasing the different cultural identities amidst intercultural space for economic means. A certain atmosphere the Trinidad carnival has created and which is appropriated by the Nigerian carnival of Calabar is that of economic enhancement. The question of economic value in the Trinidad carnival could be gleaned from Riggio’s words (1998:20) ‘Carnival is not at bottom a commercial enterprise, many members of the middle class are deeply committed to carnival, though as a force it challenges the efficiency and the profit motive that drives international commerce’. Technically, there is a progression from the pre-Lenten festival to the contemporary composition which obviously creates revenue.

The entrepreneurial spirit that hovers in the arena of carnival brings to mind the fact that for the people and the land to advance economically, they should develop a source of how that society can be reborn by exploring all the dimensions of the art systems in their culture, thus making use of what exists in these cultural practices for financial advancement. All these, is manifest in the Calabar Carnival of Nigeria. The attempt in this paper is to explore the evolutionary processes that set the Calabar carnival as example of performance as enterprise.

The Carnival Calabar: Origin

In 2000, the Carnival Calabar as the Calabar carnival is called was born in the city of Calabar the capital city of Cross River state south- south region of Nigeria. It was an initiative of the then governor of the state Mr. Donald Duke, as one of the events to mark the Cross River state annual Christmas festival (also his initiative) that holds in Calabar. According to a document from the Calabar Carnival Commission (2004:1) the origin of the idea of the Carnival Calabar was a

... blend of ideas and pot-pourri of cross-cultural parade ... In acknowledgement of our ancestral history coupled with cultural similarities that exists between the Cross River state and the island of Trinidad and Tobago, care has been taken to bring back lost detail due to harsh conditions that left no room for artistic expression and differences in climatic conditions as well as the influence of foreign culture which probably deprived the African diaspora from retaining costumed content, songs, meanings and dance style.

The main objective of the carnival is to explicate some of the cultural values of the people through various art forms: dances, songs, crafts, costumes amongst others. Another objective is to use the carnival as a point of connecting the people of Cross River state through entertainment with the outside world, since the carnival showcases the traditional/cultural and natural heritage of the people of Cross River state. Presently the effort put into the preparations of the carnival shows that it is aimed at generating income for the state. The affairs of the carnival are handled by the Calabar Carnival Commission which was created to be independent from the body that handles the Christmas festivals. This commission is headed by a Director and other personnel in their bureaucratic order. However, the commission's affair falls under the umbrella of the Cross River State Tourism Bureau. With the creation of this commission, the carnival event has been taking more organized form with more developments coming inwards compared to when it first started. From 2004 edition of the carnival, there was a great sign of progression, costumed characters were added which gave depth and color to the event.

The carnival has groups known as the carnival bands. The bands have their different themes and also leaders who oversee the affairs respectively as follows:

BANDS	LEADERS	COLOURS
Bayside	Mr. Donald Duke	Blue
Freedom	Capt. Henry Brisibe	Yellow
Passion 4	Mr. Chris Agibe	Green
Master Blaster	Mr. Gershom Basse	Orange
Seagull	Senator Florence Ita-Giwa	Red

These registered bands stand to win prizes after meeting the criteria of adjudication. However, there are also non competitive bands which are not adjudicated for trophies that feature in the carnival event. These groups change as the years progress either by having others joining or by voluntary retreat.

Program of Events

From inception, Carnival Calabar has been seen as one of the events that constitute the Christmas festival held from 1st December- 31December every year, the preparations of which start from August to November. The carnival event functions in a way that it has become a key component of the main festival, as we learn from the documents of the commission.

The screening of the participants for the Carnival Calabar pageant starts from August to November. In October, some part of November and December is three-day dry runs which have members of the five competing carnival bands rehearsing along the carnival route. This rehearsal is organized by the commission as an exercise to help band members and their officials familiarize themselves with the carnival route while preparing for the task of the main event. This process does not involve the interpretation of their theme for the year; neither does it require them to put on their costume for the main event. Other rehearsals come around this period but exclusively by individual bands.

Also in November is the essay competition in secondary and tertiary institutions on the theme of the carnival. The state's steps to involving these carnival contents in both secondary and tertiary schools by introducing an

essay competitions and the aspiration to introduce carnival curriculum in schools are part of an extensive mandate to safeguard the cultural and economic concerns of the people. Through this association, the state and the students work together to understand the important objectives for contextualizing cultural retention and economic development.

To borrow from Rex Nettleford (2003:70) the process preserves the state's natural and evolved asset and promotes interest in culture among the varied segments of the population and also stimulates and disseminates literary and artistic expressions of the creative imagination. Above all, it encourages the foundation for serious education and training in the different branches of the arts and their related disciplines. This explicitly allows for the generation of unseen potentialities from the younger generation who will automatically take up the development scene of the future.

In December there is a one day dry run for children's carnival. As with the adult rehearsals, this helps the children to get used to the carnival routes, but beyond that, it also encourages and energizes them to do better with the very hope that 'yea the carnival is here'. 1st December is used to commemorate the World's Aids Day, where usually the city walk against HIV/AIDS which feature the government functionaries, international organizations, non-governmental organizations and voluntary agencies within and outside the state including members of the five competing carnival bands and others involved. Among the strong features is the Carnival Calabar Queen pageantry, Grand Finale /Dinner, a cultural parade on December 26th and 27th between 7am and 12noon. In this, cultural parade from over 12 states and resident communities' in Cross River state are presented. From 1 pm to 4pm is the children's carnival with over 11, 000 costumed children on a 6km carnival route. Mbre Mbre (street party) - a band fete starts at 7pm and goes on till dawn. Adult road march is on the 27th December. It featured about forty thousand costumed revelers in fancy costumes of African and diasporic origin on a 12km carnival route from 7pm to midnight. The whole structural organization of the carnival event has the children carnival as the first activity, and then comes the cultural parade which involves the masquerades and then the parade by the bands.

Performances: the cultural and intercultural elements.

A critical character of the carnival structure lies in its use of variety of forms to create a spectacle of entertainment. The different colors, modes of costumes and presentations by the various bands and other partakers of the event express an atmosphere of creativity, invoke remembered tradition and give rein to the collective construction of culture and thus entertaining the spectators.

Performance arts in their nature and usage are distinguished by potentials and possibilities, apart from the ways in which the spatial dimension defines and shapes the art, but also in the way it represents in normal traditional circumstances have social implications. These implications reflect purposes and arts expressing and maintaining communality and a link of identity.

The performances that featured in the carnival event are an admixture of traditional art forms of the Cross River state people, those of the surrounding cultures and international influences. Nevertheless the theme of the carnival is woven around local issues of the land. For example, past carnivals featured models of the major landmarks of the state like their major export commodity-cocoa pods. Also featured are the low land Gorilla of the lost rain forest of West Africa which is also in Cross River State and the Ekpe cultural groups among other elements crucial to the history of the people.

The different bands respond to the festival's thematic thrust by bringing out the meaning and interpretation of their presentations using different art forms that they think suits the occasion. These bands may use various art forms like the Ekpe masquerade to capture, for instance, the European invasion of that part of the country, what they invaders encountered and how each reacted to the situation then. However undeserving this is, the attempt is to be different and be competitively attractive through stylized and unique dances to music, songs, drama, spectacle, crafts, masque, masquerades and so on. One of the unique features in the carnival is the trado -cultural groups among the bands thus giving the carnival further enrichment. The traditional originality and the African cultural content of a successful color blend that excites the spirit and heightens the imagination are present in the carnival venue.

The main feature which forms part of the adjudication criteria is the cultural parade- which tend to not only promote the culture and the traditions of the people but also serves as an avenue to advertise and trade and at the same time promote ventures. The Ekpe masquerade performances take over the stage of the carnival arena on the day assigned for the cultural parade; different cultural groups from different states of the federation take part in this, showcasing their individual ethnic/regional or tribal cultures. This particular event takes place a day before the main carnival parade which have the five bands and others performing. These performances of the masquerades and cultural dances and songs among other things are not on band basis but on troupe basis.

In order to create this melting pot of tradition- performance and enterprise, the carnival utilizes an eclectic repertoire of western, eastern, Caribbean and African materials to give a variegated rendition. To this end the music featured heavy Hip hop style. This is not only so that it appeals to the taste of the contemporary audience and foreigners who form part of the majority of the spectators but elates the spirit of the carnival. Local musical renditions are energized with the rhythms of Hip hop which produces a carnivalesque feeling as well as provide an eloquent vehicle for propelling the parade and drumming the spirit of dance, movement and revelry. No music and dance no carnival is analogous to no man without a soul. While the indigenous music and dance trail the projection and affirmation of identity and culture marketing possibly one of the definite aims of their participation, (this paper is raising as the main aim of the carnival), the Hip hop expresses the carnival ideal- inversion, the fusion of performer and spectator, denial of hierarchy and status quo and creation of a space free of official order (Bakhtin, 1982). This projects the fact ‘that carnival is not a spectacle seen by the people; they live in it, and everyone participates because its very idea embraces all the people’ (Counsell 2001:217).

As a way of maintaining and retaining their cultural heritage, the carnival emphasizes the presentation of cultural parade; featuring cultural arts, crafts, costumes, music, dance and other elements that can be traced to the traditional roots of the people all of which are allowed unfettered expression in a cocktail of presentation and rendition. This underscores the reality that the carnival is reclamation of tradition. A subtle invitation to know that ‘indigenous cultures must, therefore, be taken to mean concrete, present-day cultures of the people at the base of society, (Verhelst1992:83)

not a vestigial practice awaiting extinction with global transformation. The feature showcases the cultural values of the people and their amenability to handle cultural diversity, thus allowing other 'nationalities' in Nigeria to participate. The aim is to create awareness of the existence of this culture and also a deeper understanding of these cultures, not from the way it has been projected by foreign religion or early colonialist intimidations and exigent views. But to sum it up with Thierry G. Verhelst, (1992:83-84) words: 'to make available, especially to grassroots groups, the concepts...facts that help, in the most concrete manner possible, to reaffirm threatened identities and if possible to make innovation based on their own identity'.

Costume and Colours

While the different bands are identified by their different colors, colors also go a long way to add to the interpretation of various themes which the carnival tends to explicate. The costumes on their side are also an integral element of interpretation. It ranges from locally made materials to imported fabrics and fashion, especially collections from Europe, Caribbean and oriental world and others of the African descent. The costumes and colors may change based on the details of the themes the various bands want to interpret. These costumes are built as significant narratives to the idea of the theme a particular band tends to interpret, irrespective of the band's color identification.

Over the years, costume has been used in the carnival to create suggestive presence of nature with its accompanying elemental color. In one of the past carnival enactment on the theme of environment, green colors and fabrics of green colors were used to represent the ideal environment while colors like red and brown were used to portray the hazards and effects of carelessness and neglect on the environment. However, elaborate costumes of European and Caribbean origin has been utilized for the carnival kings and queens both of senior and junior category.

For example, in the 2007 edition of the carnival event, Mr. Donald Duke the leader of the Bay side Band and also the public initiator of the carnival appeared in the carnival in the company of his wife in attire nearing the description of the classical Roman lords but with contemporary furnishings and elaborations. While locally made costumes is predominant

among the masquerades. T-shirts with different inscriptions as 'Divas too have fun', 'Am A carnival Queen' 'Its Carnival time' and so many others are mostly worn by all categories of people, spect-actors, foreigners and indigenes alike. However, it is difficult to differentiate a foreigner in the carnival world where everyone is 'easing up in free play'. So costumes transcend the usual element of representation and goes to the interpretation of different thematic specification and the social structures they try to interpret. Since it is life beyond the ordinary, all colors appear camivalesque.

The uniqueness of the Calabar carnival lies neither in its nostalgic recourse to a fading past, nor in unnecessary cultural glorification, but in the very dynamism of performance, the ability to borrow and domesticate other performative forms that gives both the borrowed and the local equal legitimacy. On the whole, the performers at the carnival are the registered and the unregistered bands. Anyone from any nationality can register with the band of her/his choice. The cultural performances are also open to any group from all the states of the federation that will sign in for the event. For the bands performances, the band members claim the stage at their specific time and others can participate according to the wave of excitement transmitted through the performances, costume, sounds, music, dances, amongst others.

Performing Enterprise

Within the ambience of the carnival event is the spectacle of enterprise in its various manifestations. The nature of the Calabar Carnival performance is distinguished by much potential. One of this is the way in which the spatial dimensions of the event contribute to define and shape the event. Ordinarily enterprise is often situated within markets in local parlances. And markets in that context are of necessity physical spaces for buying and selling. In a sense therefore, the varied spaces of the Calabar carnival is both a located market as well as a processional one. In this sense the spaces created or defined by the carnival reflects the idea of the market and therefore beholds of it the permissiveness to act like one.

What the carnival does by this implication is to define a new context in which the performances or performers can earn money. However beyond this are the fora for unprecedented trading and selling opportunities for arts, 'rafts, food, drinks or souvenirs. Sales of souvenir here implies the different

indigenous products of Nigeria and even African origin. Produce are brought into the city with assurance that the multitude of people who come into the city are sure to purchase them.

These components of the carnival are a proven recipe for business venture: the instances where additional hotels are built to provide accommodation for the growing number of people who come into the city during and around this time. This is a strategy for business creation. The different costume, crafts especially those of traditional origin encode elements to produce market goods and services. Self employment is thus encouraged by this event as the atmosphere creates jobs and thus aids the economy of the state as the nation in general. It is a good time for one who has innovative ideas to transform them to profitable activities in the production of goods and services. The carnival Calabar is a strategy of instigating change and creating job opportunities.

Small businesses like vending of pure water are an indispensable part of the carnival economy. Add to the income from costume design, from the making of the adornments, from the different set constructions and you can come away with the tag of vigorous economic activity that stimulates local enterprise.

Therefore, carnival in this case is the subversion of hegemony of the dramatic or theatrical status quo- a perception that sees performance merely as bodily physicalisation. Instead it evokes the whole gamut of human existence- a fora for a debate and discussion of communal issues, a terrain for expressing freedom, an occasion for re-establishing rootedness and even more opportunity for enterprise either in making money or in innovativeness.

According to a report from the State Tourism Board, all capital generating sectors have grown to between 40 and 65% since the inception of the carnival. There are new investments around town like the souvenir shops, increase in transport fares in intra- town taxis, building of new hotels and guest houses, resorts, new talents in arts, crafts and music, photographers and recharge card sellers. More banks are springing up, fast food joints, supermarkets and local musical artists. The report states that in the middle of December 2007 there was beer scarcity in the whole city, so efforts were made to get to neighboring states like Akwa-Ibom and Abia

States to meet the high demand of beer in the city. Another visible income generating enterprise is the Cross River State Exams Village Venue. In there are about 200- 250 booths constructed for the 30days business enterprise in December at Calabar. This enterprise started in 2006. Each booth cost ranges from 20.000 to 80.000 and 120.000 naira for the period of 30days that the carnival lasts. A report from the Research/Planning and Statistics Department of the Commission gave an approximate number of two million visitors in attendance at the last (2008) carnival. About 10 million local and international viewership and hopes to expect about 5million visitors in the next event due to the well covered publicity it has received. This is in addition to 700,000 revellers as against the 2008 that recorded 37.559 revellers as follows:

Seagull	2359
Freedom	3000
Passion 4	7500
Bayside	5000
Master blaster	% 9700 (Gab Onah, Director Calabar Carnival Commission, “ statistics of carnival revelers”)

Seen this way, enterprise is a purposeful undertaking which serves as the beneficiary of the undertaking. The enterprise quality of the carnival is part and parcel of the carnival experience. Key to this quality is what Leff (1975:529) detailed as entrepreneurship

... the capacity for innovation, investment and activist expansion in new markets, products and techniques.

As such entrepreneurship may reflect superior information and, perhaps more importantly by imagination, which are ignored or rejected by other investors”(Anyanwu 1999:7).

All these and more are the potentials as showcased by the Calabar carnival aptly described by the initiators as the largest street party in Africa.

Performance arts in Nigeria have done much in accelerating individual and group solidarity and economic development. In earlier

centuries practices like the Egungun ancestor worship were utilized to entertain the elites in the court. Period of gradual progression enlarged its horizon as it began to satisfy grassroots people's desire for entertainment outside the original customary thing it stood for. By breaking out this way such performances began to earn money and as such began to give vent to self-expression and experimentation outside the original context.

With the awakening to the potential of reaping economic opportunities some artists created the traveling theatre style performances which take a mixture of traditional performances and dramatic renditions for financial purposes. The best example of this was Ogunde who started the business of professional theatre from the brinks of Alarinjo- a traditional Yoruba performative form.

According to Adedeji, (in Ogunbiyi 1981:244) 'Ogunde introduced some modifications which are reflections of his Christian outlook and contemporary viewpoint'. Ogunde plunged into the hazards of professionalism with his African Music Party in 1945... He did not just modify a tradition that was declining with the advent of forces like Christianity and Islam, he used it to address social issues, explicate theological learnings as well as advance capital creation for himself and his workers and subsequently other itinerant artists after himself.

Duro Ladipo also followed alongside the traditional activities of the Egungun. According to him; '...I showed keen interest in traditional Yoruba culture and customs, as amplified by the fact that I followed closely the activities of the different masquerades and cults...' (Ogunbiyi 1981:334)

Carnival Calabar in the light of empirical evidence did not completely trace itself to the roots of traditionalism as in the case of the Alarinjo and the Ogunde theatre amongst others, however, it was spurred by the cultural similarities between the Cross River state people and that of the people of the twin-island of Trinidad and Tobago. It now functions in a way that it yields money for the state, the artist and other people who have utilized the opportunity available from it. Carnival Calabar has created the assurance of the confidence of the consumer by the various ways the organizers have experimented and presented the various performances. It is also attracting investment at high levels.

Conclusion

Despite the increase in the manufacture of the 'alternative' to live performances, there still exist forms in which the live performance can still pull people not only from their homes but from far away continents. Carnival Calabar is one of the events which have proved the efficacy of this potential. With its nearly one decade of existence, it has not only remained consistent but has grown in the capacity nearly ousting the tradition that informed it, in number of spectators available for the event, media coverage, investors, sponsors and performances. A significant factor that accounts for the success of the carnival is the way in which it promotes enterprise to various categories of people.

Carnival Calabar exerts the internal strategy needed to drive the resources of the land for international market. The visitors/people who come in can recognize appropriate potentials available but untapped for their own use. There are increase returns on the sales of items brought into the state at that period of time.

The carnival retains an optimal leverage for carrying an overall business opportunity in the whole state and its neighbours, since the strategic objectives needed to provide enlightenment to what exists in the state are made available. Such includes the availability of mobility for all who may want to visit the very many tourism centers like the Obudu cattle ranch, the Abokim water falls, Tinapa trade center and whole lots of it.

So far, the Carnival Calabar has recorded tremendous success that tends to prove its efficacy to be a major component of the tourism industry by attracting more people to the state which would ultimate generate a lot of investments. However, the commission and the Tourism management body have marked appropriate strategies needed to build effective links of sustainability and continued meaningful enterprise for economic improvement from the carnival. Thus there are changes and innovations in this highly valuable event in Cross River state and in the country in general which include improvement in the growing popularity of a fuller range of the arts represented in the carnival culture and exhibition. Thus the National Tourism Development Commission through a statement by the Director advises that all other states of the federation should not organize official carnivals but rather synergize with Cross River State to bring up this

carnival up to/or make it competitive with carnivals known worldwide. This call may not be a counsel of perfection, but this step suggested by the federal government will only increase the substance of the carnival event, thus making it second largest revenue supplier for the nation after the major income generating means-oil. It would not in any way affect other performance enterprises in the country wherever they may spring since none had existed at such an entrepreneurial scale.

Arguably, Carnival Calabar can be taken as an alternative proprietor and propeller for enterprise in Nigeria. It creates an arena where investors' take entrepreneurial risks by exploring avenues in tourism construct. A proven fact is that the large number of people that it attracts make it a major revenue supplier, a source of business growth where entrepreneurs seize the opportunity to invest and alleviate economic problems. From a report from the Tourism Bureau: Two million people came into the state with different reasons in 2008 an estimated number of three million and above are expected in the coming 2009 carnival (Mr William Bassey, supervisor Operations). Moribund businesses in the region have been affected positively as many people are becoming aware of what obtains in the region. Another fact is that other businesses are attracted in the sense that the high number of people that come for the carnival make it possible for people to start up investment at various levels. For example, the hospitality industry is expanding to provide additional accommodation and meal sources that can complement the high number of population in attendance. It is also a period of business boom for transporters both air, land and water. An interesting thing is how the whole carnival is uniting all the communities and cultures in Cross River State, How other tourism sites like the Abokim waterfall, Obudu cattle ranch Tinapa trade centre and others are enjoying the patronage of the people that come for the carnival. Above all, the people are returning to the cultural oneness of communality which has always characterized the African society. Thus one can say that the carnival even though is a new or had come in new form in Nigeria is replicating the Prestine ways of doing performances and festivals which have always existed but are declining with the global turn of events. In essence beyond artistic performance, the calabar carnival is more than anything else a performance of enterprise both in creativity (innovativeness) and commerce

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Interviews with:

Mr Essien Ita Archibong, Head of Department; ICT Unit CCC on the 3rd of March (13.35pm) and 17th of July (16.20pm) 2009 at Okoi Arikpo House Calabar.

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Mr Ibok Ekpenyong, Commissioner for Planning, Research and Statistics. CCC on the 17th of July, 2009 at Okoi Arikpo House Calabar at (9.30am)

Mr Williams Bassey, Cross River State Tourism Bureau on the 17th of July, 2009 at Okoi Arikpo House Calabar at (8.20AM)